

YOUTH PERCEPTIONS, ASPIRATIONS AND DIGITAL INFLUENCE ON MIGRATION INTENTIONS OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the perceptions, digital media exposure, and migration aspirations and intentions of undergraduate students in Nigeria. A descriptive cross-sectional self-administered on-line survey using the mobile app Kobo Toolbox to generate data from 427 undergraduate students of the University of Calabar via the convenience sampling technique was conducted over four weeks. Data revealed that the mean age of participants was 23.0 ± 3.9 years. Of the 427 respondents, over half frequently come across content on social media portraying migration or life abroad positively, with majority expressing dissatisfaction with opportunities for education and employment in the country. Also, over half aspires to pursue further studies or work abroad. Digital media plays a significant role in shaping migration perceptions, aspirations and intentions. Despite being in school, one third of the students are already actively planning, and one fifth are currently considering migrating abroad for study, work and other reasons, with more than half motivated by better job prospects. Deliberate interventions to improve the economic opportunities in the country to curb the migration push factors should be considered by policy makers and other stakeholders.

Keywords: Digital media, migration aspirations, migration intentions, migration perceptions, undergraduate

BACKGROUND

Nigeria's youth migration intentions, particularly among undergraduates, are shaped by a complex and dynamic set of socio-economic challenges, institutional disruptions, and the accelerating impact of digital media (Obiechina, 2023). Japa, a Yoruba term meaning to run, escape or flee, is currently used to indicate the growing desire of Nigerian youth to migrate (Obiechina, 2023). According to Adegoke (2023), the attractiveness of Japa is mostly supported by the wealthy lifestyles that diasporan Nigerians frequently display on social media; immaculate streets, well kept lawns, shopping centres and above all constant power, which is something most Nigerians only see on TV and movies. This Japa movement intensified during the late 1980s and early 1990s, coinciding with the country's deep economic recession and the implementation of structural adjustment programs, which destabilized key sectors of society (Taylor, 2024). The consequences of this migration for Nigeria are substantial, as pointed out

by Onah et al (2022), Nigerian physician training for instance is mostly funded by the government, thus when domestically trained doctors leave the country, the nation loses money.

Extensive research across the healthcare sector demonstrates that emigration intentions are strongly tied to systemic shortcomings ranging from substandard infrastructure and unsafe work environments to inadequate compensation and limited professional growth opportunities (Obi-Ani et al. 2023; Ojo et al., 2023,). A large-scale survey of over 2,000 medical and nursing students found that 72.9% intended to practice abroad, with 32.7% unlikely to return to Nigeria. The primary drivers included the pursuit of advanced training (97.7%), improved working conditions, and better career prospects (Oyedokun, 2025). Additional studies confirm that the continued migration of health professionals is linked to the deterioration of institutional standards and support systems (Ojo et al., 2023).

The broader educational environment has also been affected. Recurring university strikes have eroded academic stability, sometimes delaying degree completion by multiple years (Taylor, 2024). Qualitative investigations into middle-class Nigerian youth suggest that Japa is often a direct response to “extremely delayed temporalities,” a term used to describe the psychological toll of unpredictable academic progress. As one respondent stated: “We suffer a lot... Nigeria has tired me” (Taylor, 2024:12). Such delay-induced demoralization positions migration not merely as a strategic choice but as essential for psychological relief and future security.

Social media modulates the migration discourse, acting both as an amplifier of aspirational narratives and as an informational resource. In addition to increasing awareness of opportunities around the world, social media often fosters a sense of inadequacy and dissatisfaction with local circumstances (Jayakody et al, 2025). Empirical evidence from a survey of 470 youth in Abuja demonstrated that social media moderately influences attitudes and norms surrounding international migration (Obiechina, 2023). Similarly, a study of youth in Ogun State found that social media reinforces idealized versions of Japa, often glossing over the realities of return migration (Odunlami et al., 2025). Scholars caution that such platforms risk presenting a one-dimensional view of migration and recommend balanced reporting to temper uncritical enthusiasm (Ekorugue et al., 2024).

Conversely, qualitative research among Nigerian emigrants revealed that social media does not always serve as a strong motivational trigger. For these individuals, trust in migration decisions is centered on kinship ties and offline networks, while economic and personal pressures exert greater influence than online portrayals (Adegoke, 2023). In summary, the migration intentions of Nigerian undergraduates reflect a nexus of structural deprivations, economic volatility, professional stagnation, and academic delays interwoven with powerful but mediated digital discourses. Social media platforms shape perceptions indirectly, constructing aspirational frameworks that may not fully capture the lived complexities of migration experiences or the possibility of return (Obiechina, 2023; Odunlami et al., 2025). The influence of social media on the migration of Nigerian youths have been research by several scholars (Adegoke, 2023; Obiechina, 2023) but limited study among undergraduate students. This gap is especially pronounced in undergraduate focused migration research, where most studies either adopt local or sectoral perspectives and rarely capture the nationwide, digitally embedded aspirations of this demographic. Addressing this lacuna is both theoretically and practically significant: theoretically, it enriches understanding of migration intention formation

at the nexus of personal experience, social influence, and digital culture; practically, it provides policymakers, educators, and youth advocates with evidence to design targeted interventions that balance aspiration with grounded awareness, thereby mitigating the structural and perceptual drivers of brain drain.

Theoretical framework

This study integrates structural, communicative, and individual agency approaches to offer a multifaceted understanding of Nigerian undergraduates' migration aspirations, drawing on a variety of migration and media theories.

Push–Pull Theory (Lee, 1966)

Lee's (1966) Push–Pull Theory remains a seminal framework for understanding migration dynamics. The theory posits that migration decisions are driven by the interaction between push factors, such as economic hardship, political instability, unemployment, and insecurity in the country of origin, and pull factors, including enhanced educational opportunities, better employment prospects, political stability, and a higher quality of life in destination countries (Nsengiyumva, 2013). Lee also introduces the concept of intervening obstacles, which may include geographical distance, immigration policies, and a lack of information that can hinder or redirect migration flows. While the model offers a clear structural lens, scholars have noted that it may oversimplify the complexity of modern migration, particularly in contexts where transnational networks, digital communication, and identity politics play substantial roles (de Haas, 2011; Obi-Ani et al., 2023). Nonetheless, its adaptability to diverse contexts has sustained its relevance in migration studies. Migration usually happens as a result of a combination of this push and pull factors... [but] flows between two places may not develop if intervening obstacles exist between them. (Lee, 1966: 51)

The Media System Dependency (MSD)

This theory, proposed by Ball-Rokeach and DeFleur (1976), posits that the extent to which individuals rely on media for information, orientation, and social utility is directly related to the potential influence that media can exert. In unstable socio-political and economic contexts, media dependency tends to increase, amplifying the media's role in shaping perceptions and decision-making (Ball-Rokeach & DeFleur, 1989). In Nigeria, persistent economic challenges and political uncertainty have driven many youths to rely heavily on digital platforms, especially social media, for migration-related information. Through these platforms, young people access narratives, advice, and perceived opportunities abroad, which may either enhance informed decision-making or propagate idealized portrayals that omit potential risks (Obi, Bartolini, & D'Haese, 2023).

However, by integrating Push–Pull Theory with MSD Theory, this study adopts a multi-level analytical approach:

Macro-level: Push–Pull Theory explains structural drivers (e.g., economic hardship, insecurity) and attractors (e.g., perceived opportunities abroad) that underpin migration aspirations.

Meso-level: MSD Theory highlights the role of media systems in shaping how youth perceive, interpret, and prioritize these push-and-pull factors.

Interactional Layer: This depends on the degree of reliance and confidence in media sources; media can either reinforce, skew, or contradict people's impressions of push-pull dynamics. Hence, this integrated framework acknowledges that Nigerian undergraduates' migration intentions are not solely determined by socio-economic conditions, but are also shaped by the mediated realities constructed through sustained engagement with digital media. In doing so, it provides both a structural and communicative lens for interpreting the "Japa" phenomenon in contemporary Nigeria.

Despite the vast amount of literature on migration from Nigeria, a large portion of it is still fragmented and frequently isolates particular drivers rather than addressing the interaction of several factors. For instance, prior research has looked at socioeconomic limitations as general factors influencing young migration (Afolayan, 2021) and the professional departure of healthcare professionals as a sector-specific example of brain drain (Okafor, 2021). Other studies have emphasized how digital platforms influence migration narratives, demonstrating how social media serves as a conduit for idealized depictions of life overseas as well as a source of useful information (Dekker & Engbersen, 2014; Obi, Bartolini, & D'Haese, 2023).

Study Objectives

The study aims to:

Examine undergraduate students' perceptions of educational and employment opportunities in Nigeria.

Identify the aspirations of undergraduate students after graduation, including their preferred career or educational pathways.

Assess the influence of digital media exposure on students' perceptions and aspirations regarding migration.

Determine the relationship between digital media content and migration intentions among undergraduate students.

Explore the main motivations and concerns influencing migration decisions among undergraduate students in Nigeria.

Research Questions

How do undergraduate students perceive the current opportunities for education and employment in Nigeria?

What are the main aspirations of undergraduate students after graduation?

How frequently do students access migration-related content on digital media platforms?

To what extent does exposure to digital media shape students' perceptions and aspirations regarding migration?

What are the main motivations and concerns influencing migration intentions among undergraduate students?

Methodology

Study design, sample and setting

A descriptive cross-sectional self-administered on-line survey using the mobile app Kobo Toolbox was conducted between July 31st and 25th August 2025 to survey to 427

undergraduate students in the university of Calabar via convenience sampling technique using the student online WhatsApp groups. Post graduate students were excluded.

Sample size

The Leslie Kish formula (1965) was used to estimate the sample size, employing a standard normal deviate of 1.96 corresponding to a 95% confidence level. An estimated proportion of 60% of youths influenced by social media on the migration aspirations, based on Obiechina (2023), and a desired precision level of 5% were applied. Accounting for a 15% attrition rate, the minimum sample was estimated at 424.

Data processing and analysis

The data generated were exported and analysed using the Stata 18 version. Descriptive variables were presented in tables as percentages and frequencies.

Ethical consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from the University of Calabar Research Ethical Review Board, Directorate of Research and Development, University of Calabar (UC/DR&D/RERB/56).

Results

Data from 427 respondents were analyzed. Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The mean age of participants was 23.0 ± 3.9 years, with 341 (79.9%) aged less than 25. There were 219 (51.3%) females, and 252 (59.0%) were in their fourth year of study. Additionally, 339 (79.4%) resided off campus. One hundred and twelve (26.2%) were students in the Faculty of Clinical Sciences.

Among the respondents, 153 (35.83%) were dissatisfied and 105 (24.59%) were very dissatisfied with the opportunities for education and employment in the country. One hundred and seventy-five (41.08%) aspired to pursue further education abroad, while 271 (63.47%) viewed migration as very important for achieving personal and professional goals (Table 2).

Results in Table 3 indicate that 253 (59.25%) of the respondents use social media platforms multiple times a day, with 221 (51.76%) frequently encountering content on social media portraying migration or life abroad positively. Two hundred and sixty two (61.36%) reported that information on scholarship and jobs were the migration related-contents on digital media with the greatest impact.

Students who perceived digital media as strongly influencing their views about migrating numbered 180 (42.15%). Additionally, 224 (52.46%) and 157 (36.77%) of respondents were considering and actively planning respectively, to migrate abroad for study, work and other reasons such as business. Among the main motivations for considering migration, 269 (63.00%), 238 (55.74%), and 185 (43.33%) reported better job prospects, better educational opportunities and higher standard of living, respectively as their main motivations. Further, 281 (66.12%) identified financial constraints as their primary concerns about migrating abroad (Table 4).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of respondents

Characteristics	N = 427 (%)
Age in years, mean \pm SD	23.0 \pm 3.9
Age group	
<25	341 (79.9)
>25	86 (20.1)
Sex	
Male	208 (48.7)
Female	219 (51.3)
Year of study	
Year 1	10 (2.3)
Year 2	60 (14.1)
Year 3	63 (14.8)
Year 4	252 (59.0)
Year 5	35 (8.2)
Year 6	7 (1.6)
Place of residence	
On campus	88 (20.6)
Off campus	339 (79.4)
Faculty	
Agriculture	12 (2.8)
Allied Medical Sciences	44 (10.3)
Arts and Humanities	14 (3.3)
Arts and Social Science Education	5 (1.2)
Basic Medical Sciences	42 (9.8)
Biological Sciences	21 (4.9)
Clinical Sciences	112 (26.2)
Computing	4 (0.9)
Dentistry	16 (3.8)
Engineering	12 (2.8)
Education	1 (0.2)
Environmental Sciences	3 (0.7)
Institute of Education	1 (0.2)
Law	7 (1.6)
Management Sciences	11 (2.6)
Medical Laboratory Sciences	37 (8.7)
Pharmacy	20 (4.7)
Physical Sciences	2 (0.5)
Science Education	1 (0.2)
Social Sciences	62 (14.5)

Table 2: Student perceptions on education and employment opportunities and post-graduation aspirations

Variables	Number (427), n (%)
Rate of satisfaction with opportunities for education and employment in the country	
Very satisfied	23 (5.39)
Satisfied	37 (8.67)
Neutral	109 (25.53)
Dissatisfied	153 (35.83)
Very dissatisfied	105 (24.59)
Main aspirations after graduation	
Further education in the country	32 (7.51)
Further education abroad	175 (41.08)
Get employment in the country	74 (17.37)
Get employment abroad	127 (29.81)
Engage in entrepreneurship	90 (21.13)
Others	24 (5.63)
Importance of migration to achieving personal or professional goals	271 (63.47)
Very important	122 (28.57)
Somewhat important	22 (5.15)
Not important	12 (2.81)
Not sure	

Table 3: Digital media exposure and its influence on migration perceptions

Variables	Number (427), n (%)
Frequency of use of social media platforms	
Several times a day	253 (59.25)
Daily	160 (37.47)
Weekly	7 (1.64)
Rarely	6 (1.41)
Never	1 (0.23)
Having come across content on social media that portrays migration or life abroad positively	
Frequently	
Occasionally	221 (51.76)
Rarely	154 (36.07)
Never	46 (10.77)
Extent of digital media influence on views about migrating	
Strongly influence	180 (42.15)
Somewhat influence	144 (33.72)
Little influence	73 (17.10)
No influence	30 (7.03)
Type of migration-related content with greatest impact	
Success stories/testimonials	195 (45.67)

Information about scholarships/jobs	262 (61.36)
News about migration policies	58 (13.58)
Challenges and risks abroad	75 (17.56)
Advice from peers or influencers	55 (12.88)
Other	2 (0.47)

Table 4: Students migration intentions

Variables	Number (427), n (%)
Currently considering migrating abroad for study, work, or other reasons Yes, actively planning	157 (36.77)
Yes, considering	224 (52.46)
No, not considering	46 (10.77)
Main motivations for considering migration	
Better educational opportunities	238 (55.74)
Better job prospects	269 (63.00)
Higher standard of living	185 (43.33)
Family reunification	57 (13.35)
Adventure/new experiences	126 (29.51)
Other	9 (2.1)
Main concerns about migrating abroad	
Financial constraints	281 (66.12)
Legal/visa issues	189 (44.47)
Cultural adaptation	72 (16.94)
Safety/security	77 (18.12)
Lack of information/support	85 (20.00)
Other	10 (2.35)

Discussion

This study examined the perceptions, digital media exposure, and migration aspirations and intentions of undergraduate students in Nigeria. The findings provide insights into these students' aspirations and influences shaping migration intentions.

The results revealed that six in ten undergraduate students are dissatisfied with the opportunities for education and employment in the country, with about 70.9% expressing aspirations for further studies or employment abroad after graduation. Better job prospects (63.00%) were the top reason for considering migration in our study. This finding aligns with a previous study by Essien et al. (2023) which highlighted financial consideration as the major pull factor. The growing importance of pull factors and global opportunities in shaping youths' aspirations and ambitions is evident. According to Ekhorugue et al. (2024), many people have been forced to seek better opportunities elsewhere due to high unemployment, low income, and inadequate economic development.

The study revealed that digital media is a critical factor shaping and influencing undergraduate students' migration perceptions and aspirations. The result shows that digital media strongly influences about 42.15% of the respondent's views on migration. This rate is higher than the 16% high influence reported by Obiechina (2023) in a study in Abuja. This difference might be attributed to the demographics as the current study focused solely on undergraduate students who aspire to migrate for further studies, not just for employment

opportunities. Obiechina (2023) also reported that social media messages are more likely to affect migration desires among those with higher levels of education. These differences could also be due to the fact that 56% of the respondents in Obiechina's study were employed at the time of data collection, whereas the current study's respondents are undergraduate students unsure of securing employment upon graduation. The positive migration narratives from frequent digital media use provide youths with sources of information and motivation. Results of the study revealed that nine out of ten students use the social media every day and half of the students have come across content on social media portraying migration or life abroad positively. This finding supports previous studies emphasizing the role of digital media in migration decision making and the importance of digital media content in reinforcing migration aspirations. Inyama (2021) found that the majority of young people's opinions on the availability of better employment prospects overseas are influenced by Western films and other media sources.

Though still in school, one third of the students are already actively planning, and one fifth are currently considering migrating abroad for study, work and other reasons, with more than half motivated by better job prospects. A similar trend was reported by Essien et al. (2023) in a study among early career psychiatrists in Nigeria. They found that more than three-quarters of respondents had thought of leaving Nigeria, two thirds were thinking about leaving at the time, and half had already started the migration process, estimating departure within five years. This finding also aligns with Schöfberger et al. (2020) who reported that economic considerations seem especially significant, as over half of respondents in Senegal (54%) and Cabo Verde (64%) stated that finding work was the primary reason for considering emigration between 2016 and 2018. A similar finding was reported in a qualitative study by Adegoke (2023), where some respondents indicated that social media did not influence their decision to migrate; rather the economic and social factors such as career progressions, security and job satisfaction were motivating factors. This difference with the present study may be due to the age range of participants (26 and 48 years old) and their minimum education level (a first degree), making them less susceptible to social media influence compared to the age of respondents in this study.

Among those aspiring to further their education after graduation, findings revealed that five in ten are motivated by better educational opportunities. This may be partly due to the incessant strikes by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) in Nigeria.

The study limitation is the reliance on self-reported data which may be influenced by social desirability.

Conclusion

The study examined the migration aspirations and intentions of undergraduate students in Nigeria, revealing the critical role of digital media in shaping perceptions amid limited opportunities for education, employment and improved standard of living- areas with which the majority of students expressed dissatisfaction. Positive narratives of life abroad from the media significantly influence migration related views and opinion. Addressing the structural economic challenges and improving the economic opportunities are essential interventions that could help reduce migration push factors.

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